

PRADHAN MANTRI MUDRA YOJANA: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW

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Abstract

In order to promote economic development, the Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana was established in an effort to alleviate or reduce the financial crisis among microenterprises. By uniting banks and small business owners on one platform, MUDRA serves a vital function in providing a common platform for both groups of clients. It is configured to function as a refinancing organization. Its primary objective is to give microenterprises, via last mile financiers, mudra loans up to Rs. 10,000,000 so they can begin or grow their operations. Its main objective is to refinance different last-mile financial organizations that lend money to small enterprises in the non-corporate sector, thereby supporting their growth. These financial organizations lend money to small businesses that engage in commerce, manufacturing, and agriculture-related activities. To benefit from mudra loans and fulfill the institution's mission, the borrower may contact any financial institution.

Keywords: Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana, Financial Crisis, Loans, Business

Introduction

The Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana (PMMY) represents a groundbreaking initiative launched by the Government of India in April 2015, aimed at revolutionizing access to financial resources for small and micro enterprises. Acknowledging the critical importance of these businesses in driving innovation, economic growth, and job creation, this scheme offers loans up to ₹10 lakhs, empowering aspiring entrepreneurs to transform their ideas into reality. Targeting individuals from marginalized and economically weaker sections, PMMY is designed to dismantle the barriers to entrepreneurship by providing affordable credit without the burden of collateral. This inclusive approach not only fosters a culture of self-employment but also nurtures the spirit of innovation among diverse communities. By enhancing access to finance, the initiative plays a vital role in strengthening the micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSME) sector, which is a cornerstone of India's economy. Through PMMY, the government envisions creating a vibrant ecosystem that promotes sustainable growth, enhances competitiveness, and

drives socio-economic development across the nation. Ultimately, this scheme aims to empower individuals, stimulate local economies, and pave the way for a more equitable and prosperous future.

Objectives of the Study

- ✓ To evaluate the overall effectiveness of the Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana in achieving its goals of supporting microenterprises and enhancing financial inclusion.
- ✓ To review the key findings and insights from existing literature on the scheme's performance and identify areas for future research and policy development.

Research Methodology

The nature of the work is both analytical and descriptive. A variety of national and international publications, journals, books, periodicals, websites, and other relevant material related to this field have been gathered for secondary data.

Review of Literature

1. **M. Shashid and et.al (2016)** The PMMY scheme contributes significantly to the welfare of individuals involved in small scale industries, thereby positively influencing the overall economic progress. MUDRA envisions the formalization of the informal sector, bridging the financial gap for those who have traditionally been excluded from formal financial services. Its unique selling point lies in its role as an apex refiner, facilitating low-cost financing, which is poised to address a substantial void in India's microfinance landscape
2. **Manish Agarwal and et.al(2017)** has made a study on "**Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana**".The objectives of the Study include the overview of PMMY Scheme. The Study concluded that PMMY is a great initiative taken by the Government of India, there is a big change in the area of Microfinance
3. **V. Poornima (2019)**The researcher found that the MUDRA scheme offers a fresh perspective of optimism for both established and aspiring micro enterprises and female entrepreneurs. Nurturing and advocating for these small-scale businesses represent a substantial contribution to bolstering the nation's economy. These enterprises play a pivotal role in generating employment opportunities, contributing to exports, and enhancing the GDP. Addressing the procedural challenges would

undoubtedly transform the MUDRA scheme into a pivotal force within the MSME sector.

4. **GunjanBhayanaRashmi and et al (2020)** has analyzed about the “ **Role of Mudra Yojana in entrepreneurship Development**” .The objective is to understand Conceptual building block of PMMY.The study concluded that PMMY is the key initiative taken by the Government of India to develop and improve entrepreneurial culture in the country.
5. **Deepthi George (2020)**, has critically analyzed the available data to verify whether the objectives of mudra loans are achieved and also assessed the impact of mudra scheme on the borrowers. The findings were, no much impact was there on the borrower women empowerment and the role of the Mudra loan in promoting holistic growth and development of women.
6. **Pushpender Kumar and et.al (2021)** made a study on “**Empowering women through Entrepreneurship, the Role of Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana**”.The objectives of the study states To examine the impact of Mudra loan on different indicators of womenempowerment. The finding of the study states that the Mudra loam is promoting growth and development.
7. **Tarak N. Sahu, and et.al (2021)** The study highlights the significance of MUDRA scheme, recognized as a potent poverty alleviation strategy, demonstrates its potential to uplift women in society traditionally dominated by men. The PMMY scheme has been instrumental in enhancing the livelihoods of women, fostering income generating sources, and contributing to their financial, social, and psychological development.
8. **Dr. Dattatry R Mane and et.al (2021)** made a study on “**Mudra Yojana: A Step towards Creating Growth for Women Entrepreneurs in Micro Enterprises Sector**”.The objectives of the study states that to evaluate the role of Mudra Yojana in Women Entrepreneurship Development .The Findings of the study states that found that the share of amount sanctioned was higher in FY 2015-16 for women than the men counterparts, which gradually declined in the subsequent finance.

9. **YogeshMahajan (2021)**, has studied the impact of Mudra loans on small businesses. The enterprises are benefitted from no collateral loans but the conclusion was, there was no impact on the standard of living and financial independence has not achieved by the women entrepreneurs.
10. **DivyaMahadule and et.al (2022)** made a study on **“Impact of Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana on Women Entrepreneurs- A Comprehensive Review”**. The objective of the Study is to assess the Mudra Yojana components that benefit women the most. The study concluded that the Government is assisting women entrepreneurs by providing financial and other Support such as Counseling, training and Skill Development.
11. **Prof.M.Gangadhar (2022)** made an attempt to investigate about **“A study on Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana- An Overview”**.The aim of the Study is to the performance of different category under Mudra Scheme. The paper concluded that 41% of loan are borrowed by women.
12. **CharulataLonde (2022)**, has identified the role of mudra yojana scheme in Maharashtra region. The main objective of the study is to identify the bottom of period who has taken benefit of mudra loans and the growth rate obtained by women entrepreneurship and general mudra loan holders.
13. **Garima Singh and et.al (2022)** has examined a study on **“Problems faced by women of Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana scheme in Lucknowcity”**.The objective of the study states that identify the problems and constraints faced by women and banks during implementation of this scheme. The finding of the study states that women in the country by providing business loans and supporting them so that they can be financially independent and self-reliant.
14. **Varuna Agarwala and et. Al (2022)** has analyzed a study on **“Female entrepreneurship, employability and empowerment: impact of the mudra loan scheme”**.The objectives of the study states that Mudra Yojana, which supports individuals financially to start an enterprise. The finding of the study states that women could be “active agents of change” and play an important role in both the family and society.

15. **Seema Rathee and et.al (2023)** made a study on “**Transition in Employability and Women Empowerment: Substantiates from Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana**”. The objectives of the study states that analyze the influence of the PMMY scheme on employability and Women empowerment. The finding of the study states that credit amount has a big amount on creditability.
16. **Dr. N. Ramanjaneyalu and et.al. (2023)** The study revealed that the MUDRA yojana initiative has witnessed a significant increase in the participation of women as entrepreneurs, particularly in terms of opening accounts across its various components. This program has also led to the establishment of a higher number of micro and small enterprise enterprises, thereby fostering business growth. Among the three categories within the MUDRA yojana, the Shishu category stands out as the leader in terms of both the volume of accounts opened and the number of entrepreneurs it has facilitated.
17. **J. JamelaSalasty and et.al (2023)** the emergence of women entrepreneurs in India has gained momentum through the utilization of MUDRA loans, aligning with the vision of the central government to create conducive growth opportunities for women. The MUDRA yojana has made a significant positive impact on the development of women entrepreneurship and the growth of the India economy. In comparison to other business loans available to entrepreneurs, MUDRA loans are most cost effective, easily accessible, and entail minimal documentation charge.
18. **RhikKundu (2023)** made a study on “**Women Major beneficiaries of Mudra and stand up India Schemes**”. The finding of the study states that to finance green-field projects to women entrepreneurs, which goes a long way in the promotion of entrepreneurship among women.
19. **.ManishaKumari (2024)** has examined a study on “**A comprehensive analysis of pradhanmantri mudra yojana in promoting women’s empowerment through entrepreneurship development in Jharkhand**”. The objectives of the study states that evaluate the effectiveness of the MUDRA scheme in promoting women’s entrepreneurship in India, particularly in Jharkhand state. The finding of the study states that better understanding of the effectiveness of the PMMY in fostering women's entrepreneurship as a means of empowerment

20. The Role of Mudra Loans in Promoting Women Entrepreneurship this article denotes that Mudra loans stand as a beacon of empowerment, illuminating the path for women entrepreneurs in India. These financial instruments have not only shattered barriers but also ignited the flames of ambition, resilience, and economic growth.

Conclusion

Based on the comprehensive review of the Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana (PMMY), it is evident that the scheme has made significant strides in advancing financial inclusion and supporting microenterprise development in India. The PMMY has successfully bridged the financial gap for many individuals, especially women, by facilitating low-cost financing and contributing to economic growth. The program has been instrumental in fostering entrepreneurship and enhancing the livelihoods of numerous beneficiaries, demonstrating its potential as a powerful tool for economic empowerment. However, the review also highlights some variability in the scheme's effectiveness. While many studies affirm the positive impact of PMMY on employment generation and financial independence, others reveal that the anticipated outcomes, particularly in terms of women's empowerment and holistic development, have not always been fully realized. Challenges related to implementation and procedural inefficiencies have been noted, suggesting that the scheme's effectiveness could be further improved with targeted policy reforms and enhanced support mechanisms.

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